

INFORMATION FROM CHINESE SOURCES ABOUT THE MILITARY CAMPAIGN OF THE TANG EMPIRE TO TASHKENT IN 750

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Abstract. *The given article is devoted to the military campaign of the Chinese Tang Empire to Tashkent in the year 750, its causes, and consequences. The analysis of the data shows that the reason for the Tang Empire's campaign to Tashkent was its intention to gain control over Turkestan and establish dominance over trade routes passing through the region. As a result of this campaign, Tang forces suffered a defeat in a clash with the troops of the Arab Caliphate at the Talas River in 751 and were forced to abandon their aggressive plans.*

Keywords: *military campaign, Chinese sources, Tang Empire, Tibet, Pamir, Binkent, Tashkent, the state of Chach, Taraz.*

Introduction. At the end of the Sui Dynasty (581–618), the socio-economic situation in China sharply deteriorated, which led to a wave of peasant uprisings across the country. Many regional princes declared independence from central authority, and rulers of the northern provinces allied with the Turks in their struggle against the Sui ruling dynasty. One such prince was Li Yuan (李淵), the governor of the Taiyuan region (in the central part of present-day Shanxi province) [Yu Taishan 1996: 152].

In 618, with the support of the Eastern Turkic Khaganate, Li Yuan (also known as Gaozu 高祖 – founder of the dynasty, reigned from 618–626) seized the capital city of Chang'an (modern Xi'an) and declared the establishment of the new Tang Dynasty [Shang Yue 1954: 128–129], since he held the hereditary princely title "Tang Gong" (唐公 – Grand Duke of Tang). Li Yuan's receipt of Turkic support was not accidental—his ancestors lived in the Longxi region of Gansu province and had Turkic origins [Shang Yue 1954: 128; Cihai 1979: 856]. In the 9th year of his reign, he handed over the throne to his son Li Shimin (Taizong 太宗 – reigned 627–650).

Methodology. Until 628, the Tang Dynasty was occupied with suppressing scattered rebel groups and consolidating central authority. Therefore, it treated its allies—the Turks—very loyally. However, during the reign of Li Shimin and his successor Li Zhi (李治, also known as Gaozong 高宗, who ruled from 650 to 684), the Tang dynasty's policy changed completely.

In 683, Li Zhi died, and the throne was taken by his wife, Wu Zetian (武则天), who assumed the title *Emperor of Zhou* (*Wuzhou Huangdi* – Empress of the militant Zhou dynasty).

This was the result of several factors: first, she was the daughter of a high-ranking official, and second, during Li Zhi's lifetime, she was allowed to participate in discussions of state affairs. By nature, she was hostile toward the Turks. This attitude may have been influenced by family tradition, the worldview of her teachers, and the anti-Turkic rhetoric of court officials during deliberations on state matters.

After gaining real power following her husband's death, she removed two legitimate heirs to the throne one after the other, and in 690, she declared herself Empress.

During her 15-year reign (690–705), she focused primarily on fighting the Turks, Tibetans, and Khitans. On this matter, Shang Yue wrote: "Wu Zetian... in her foreign policy, took measures to oppose the Turks, Tibetans, and Khitans and strove to open the way to the western countries."

From the time Wu Zetian came to power, the Tang dynasty, showing extraordinary activity in foreign affairs, continued the traditional Chinese strategy of allying with distant enemies to combat nearby ones. It established allied relations with the Western Turkic rulers and concentrated its efforts on destroying the neighboring Eastern Turkic Khaganate.

In 705, under pressure from influential palace officials and their local supporters, Wu Zetian was forced to abdicate the throne in favor of the legitimate heir.

During the following 30 years, the economy of Tang China experienced unprecedented development, and the country's administrative system was improved. Scholars and literate individuals who passed the state examinations were appointed to government positions. The population reached 52.9 million people [Shang Yue 1954: 136]. All of this created favorable conditions for the implementation of the Sui dynasty's inherited plans to combat the Turks.

According to the Chinese historian Shang Yue, at that time, the entire territory west of the frontier point of Yumenguan ("Jade Gate" or "Jade Frontier Pass") was under Turkic control [Shang Yue 1954: 139]. This border point was established by the Western Han Empire after Emperor Wu Di's (140–85 BCE) troops seized the Hexi Corridor.

The struggle against the Eastern Turkic Khaganate brought success to the Tang Dynasty. Following this, it launched a more aggressive campaign against the Western Turkic Khaganate its troops broke through into Central Asia and, by the mid-7th century, temporarily seized the Tarim Basin region from the Western Turks.

In 658, after several years of intense military operations, the Tang forces succeeded in breaking the resistance of the Western Turkic Khaganate and, with the help of rival factions, captured the ruler of Binkent (Tashkent).

However, before the Tang Empire could consolidate its victories over the Western Turks, it came under pressure from a newly emerging state in Tibet. This Tibetan power seized control of the eastern section of the Silk Road and pushed the Tang out of what is now Eastern Turkestan and several western regions of ancient China.

According to Shang Yue, Tibet's rise occurred during the reign of the third Tang emperor, Li Zhi (Gaozong, 650–683) [Shang Yue 1954: 140]. At that time, the Tibetan population was largely composed of the Qiang (ancient pronunciation: *Kian*), who were the earliest inhabitants of the southern part of Eastern Turkestan and the Kokonor region. As a result of large-scale military campaigns by the Eastern Han dynasty in 159 CE, they were devastated, and part of the population fled to Tibet.

In the mid-7th century, the Tibetans succeeded in creating a strong state, which Chinese sources referred to as Tufan (吐蕃, ancient pronunciation *Ta-biwan*, *Tu-biwan*; also known as Tubo). This event led to a shift in the political map of the Central Asian subregion.

In 663, the Tibetans defeated the Tuyuhun tribes (吐谷渾 *tuyuhun*), who at the time inhabited the territories of modern Gansu, Qinghai, and Sichuan provinces of the People's Republic of China. The Tibetan victory led to these provinces falling under the sphere of influence of the Tubo state. The Tang Empire's attempts to defend the Tuyuhun throne and use it as a counterbalance against the Tibetans were unsuccessful.

By the mid-7th century, the Tibetans had extended their influence into the southern part of Eastern Turkestan. As a result of these developments, the Tufan (Tubo) state effectively became the dominant power over the section of the Silk Road stretching from the Tang capital of Chang'an to the cities of Turkestan.

Moreover, the Tibetan state of Tufan (Tubo) expanded its influence into several regions of the Pamirs and established close ties with India and Nepal. By 670, it had even forced the Tang court to relinquish control over some of the occupied territories in Eastern Turkestan [Yu Taishan 1996: 167–169].

In this context, the struggle against the Tibetan state of Tubo became a top priority for the Tang Empire.

However, at the same time, with the rise to power of Ilterish Qutluq (Gudolu, 682–692), the Eastern Turkic Khaganate began to actively resist the westward expansion of Tang forces. The Khaganate's resurgence continued during the reigns of Kapaghan Khagan (Mochuo, 692–716) and Bilge Khagan (Pika Kehan, 716–734).

Yet during their rule, the Eastern Turkic Khaganate changed its stance toward the Tang dynasty. With the intensification of Arab military activity in Turkestan, Kapaghan Khagan deemed it necessary to establish peace with the Tang Empire in order to avoid being caught between two fronts.

In 693, with this goal in mind, Kapaghan Khagan sent envoys to Chang'an with an offer of a truce [Wen Dujian 1990: 314]. The Tang Empire, feeling pressure from both the Turks and Tibetans, was forced to accept this proposal.

With the rise of Bilge Khagan to power, he continued the policy of maintaining peace with the Tang Empire. At the same time, he took active measures to subjugate several neighboring tribes that had previously refused to submit to the Eastern Turkic Khaganate. This situation somewhat irritated the Tang court, which was actively trying to support those Turkic tribes that resisted their supreme ruler.

At this time, the Tibetan ruler suggested to Bilge Khagan that they join forces against the Tang Empire. In an attempt to ease the Tang emperor's hostility toward him, in 727, Bilge Khagan informed the Tang court of this development. Concerned about the Tibetan ruler's intentions, the Tang emperor Xuanzong (玄宗, by name Li Longji 李隆基, who ruled from 712–755) was forced to make certain concessions to Bilge Khagan. The emperor not only refrained from opposing the Eastern Turkic ruler's actions to restore control over his former tributary tribes, but also agreed to allow him to trade within Tang territories [Wen Dujian 1990: 315].

Moreover, in 731, the Tang emperor of the 8th generation, Xuanzong (712–756), sent a group of representatives led by the military commander Zhang Chuyuan to the headquarters of the Eastern Turkic Khaganate to express condolences following the death of Bilge Khagan. Previously, Xuanzong, trying to prevent the possibility of an alliance between Bilge Khagan and Tibet, had been planning to establish family ties with the Eastern Turkic Khaganate by marrying one of his princesses to the Khagan. However, the sudden death of Bilge Khagan from poisoning prevented this plan from being realized [Wen Dujian 1990: 315].

With the continued strength of the Eastern Turkic Khaganate and Tibet's desire to form an alliance with it, the Tang Empire was unable to take active military action against the Tibetan state of Tufan (Tubo) [Wen Dujian 1990: 312–316].

After the death of Bilge Khagan, a power struggle erupted within the Eastern Turkic Khaganate. Taking advantage of this situation, the Tang court began a war against the state of Tufan (Tubo).

Between 742 and 746, the Tang Dynasty launched three military campaigns against it, but all ended in failure. In 747, the Tang court organized a military campaign to the Pamirs via Kuchar (Anxi) and Kashgar with the goal of driving the Tibetans out of the southern part of Eastern Turkestan and the Pamirs. The Tang forces were led by Gao Shanzhi, who was instructed to seize the fortified areas in the Pamirs from the Tibetans.

Within one hundred days, the Tang forces managed to pass through Aksu, Maralbashi (Barchuk), and Kashgar, reaching Shighnan (Shigénan) — on the eastern bank of the Panj River in a region where the borders of Tajikistan and Afghanistan meet. Here, Gao Shanzhi, splitting his forces into three columns, organized further military operations. One column, consisting of 3,000 cavalry under the command of Zhao Chunbi, was sent toward Lianyunbao, located near Sarhad.

The second column, commanded by Jia Chunhuang, was sent toward the red Buddhist temple (in Chinese, *Chifota*) at Bozai-Gumbaz (later named Karwan-Balasi). The third column, led by the commander himself, Gao Shanzhi, headed toward Wakhan (Migo). All three columns of the Tang forces were instructed to meet on the 13th day of the 7th month at Lianyunbao, near Sarhad. By this time, a Tibetan detachment of about 1,000 men was stationed at the fortress of Lianyunbao.

The main forces of the Tibetans, numbering 8,000 to 9,000 men, were stationed near the fortress, in a location protected by mountain ranges on all sides. After crossing the Wakhan River, the Tang forces delivered a surprise strike against the main Tibetan forces. The military actions of the Tang forces ended in a defeat for the Tibetans [Wang Zhilai 1986: 276–277]. This victory opened the way for the Tang forces to carry out further successful military operations. In August 747, they managed to capture Little Bolu (Xiao Bolu) [Zhongguo 1997: 160].

“As a decision to subdue Little Bolu,” writes Wang Zhilai, “the Tang Dynasty wanted to strike at the Tibetan forces aimed at expanding their sphere of influence, seize the gates of the western states, and establish control over the crucial trade routes passing through the four western regions” [Wang Zhilai 1986: 277], such as Karashar, Kuchar, Kashgar, and Yarkand.

The *Old History of the Tang Dynasty (Jiu Tangshu)* notes that in the 8th month of the Tianbao period (747), Gao Xianzhi captured the ruler of Bolü and his princess [Liu Xu 1956–1958: 14777 (877)/2a/].

Results and discussion. As reported in Chinese sources, after the successful military operations in the Pamirs against the Tibetans, the Tang forces, commanded by Gao Xianzhi, turned their military efforts to the northern direction. In 748, a campaign was organized against the city of Suiye (modern Tokmak) [Xinjiang 1996: 663]. The local resistance was brutally crushed, the city was captured, and it was completely destroyed. The following year, the Tang forces captured the kingdom of Kasa (Khasa), and in 750, under the command of Gao Xianzhi, they attacked the state of Chach (in Chinese sources, Shigu (石国), modern Tashkent). During the storming of the city, the local ruler Jabshi (Chebishi 車鼻施) was captured and later sent to China, where he was executed at the gates of the border post. His subordinates were also taken captive [Ou Yangxu 1956–1958: 16529(1115)/5a/].

In the *Old History of the Tang Dynasty (Jiu Tangshu)*, it is noted that after capturing the ruler of Chach and his people, the commander of the Tang forces, Gao Xianzhi, plundered his palace. Regarding this, the following is written in the text:

“[Gao] Xianzhi, showing greed, took from the state of Chach more than 10 poods (dan 石) of large lapis lazuli stones, 5 to 6 hǔrjūn of gold, many camels, famous horses, and precious jade” (仙芝性貪獲史國大塊瑟瑟十餘石真金五六駝駝名馬寶玉) [Liu Xu 1956–1958: 14777(877)/3a/].

In the *New History of the Tang Dynasty (Xin Tangshu)*, it is written: “[Gao] Xianzhi was a greedy person, and after defeating Chach (Shi), he took more than 10 poods of large lapis lazuli stones, 5 to 6 hǔrjūn of yellow gold, many camels, fine horses, and precious jade” (仙芝為人貪破石獲瑟瑟十餘斛黃金五六橐駝良馬寶玉甚) [Ou Yangxu 1956–1958: 16529(1115)/5a/].

According to the Chinese historian and author of the three-volume work *"History of Central Asia" (Zhōngyà Tōngshǐ 中亚通史)*, Wang Zhilai, Gao Xianzhi conducted a military campaign against the state of Chach (Shi-go 石国) at the request of the ruler of Fergana and under the pretext of negotiating a peace agreement. However, upon approaching the city of Tashkent, he unexpectedly launched an attack. In Chinese historical records, the actions of the Tang general are justified by the claim that the ruler of Chach had refused to "observe the proper conduct of a vassal ruler" [Wang Zhilai 2010: 278].

In his book, Wang Zhilai also provides information from the section titled *"The Narrative of Li Siyé" (李嗣业)* in the *Old History of the Tang Dynasty (Jiu Tangshu)*. One passage reads:

“Initially, [Gao] Xianzhi offered the ruler of Chach (Shi) to negotiate peace, but then, having raised his army, he launched an attack and defeated his forces. He killed the elderly and the weak, captured the young and strong, took gold, jewels, camels, horses, and other livestock. The people of the country cried out and wailed, and [he] arrested the ruler of Chach, sending him eastward to the gates of the frontier post” (初，仙芝给石国王约为和好，乃将兵袭破之，杀其老弱，虏其丁壮，取金宝瑟瑟驼马等国人号哭，因掠石国王东献之于阙下) [Wang Zhilai 2010: 278].

The son of the ruler of Tashkent managed to escape [Wang Zhilai 1986: 277]. These events are described in the works of V. V. Barthold [Barthold 1963: 254]. The son of the Tashkent ruler sought help from the Arab governor in Khorasan, Abu Muslim, who sent troops under the command of Ziyad (in Chinese sources, Zhiya) to meet the Tang army. In an effort to push the Arabs out of the region, the Tang court sent 30,000 troops (in Arab sources, more than 50,000). The decisive battle took place in 751 at the Talas River, near the modern city of Taraz (Avliya-ata), which ended in a complete defeat of the Chinese forces under Gao Xianzhi. Only a few thousand Chinese soldiers managed to escape. According to Arab sources, the Tang losses amounted to more than 50,000 men, with 20,000 taken prisoner [Wang Zhilai 1997: 42–43]. This event forced the Tang court to abandon its plans to incorporate the region into its sphere of influence. As noted by Russian academician S. L. Tikhvinsky, "for the next ten centuries, there were no Chinese troops, Chinese administration, or Chinese population west of the Great Wall of China (modern Gansu Province)" [Tikhvinsky 1996: 323].

It is worth noting that the final point of the Great Wall, as described by the scholar, corresponds to the Jiayu Pass, where, in 1372, five years after the founding of the Ming Dynasty, a fortress was built.

The Consequences of Defeat in the War with the Arabs and the Rise of An Lushan's Rebellion:

The defeat in the war with the Arabs not only negatively affected the authority of the Tang Empire but also led to a deterioration in its political and socio-economic situation. China was once again engulfed in internal political struggles and ceased to play an active role in international relations with the Central Asian states.

The famous rebellion of An Lushan, which began in 755, not only tied down all the forces of the Tang Empire but also put China in a position of dependency on the Uyghur Khaganate (744–842), which united a significant number of Turkic tribes. The Tang court was forced to ask the khaganate for help in suppressing the rebellion. In return for their assistance, the Tang court granted the khaganate privileges, effectively ensuring it free trade within China. Many traders from Turkestan began coming to Chang'an, presenting themselves as Uyghurs.

When, in 756, the main cities of Chang'an (modern-day Xi'an) and Luoyang fell into the hands of the rebels led by An Lushan, the Tang Emperor Suzong (756–762) also sought assistance from the Abbasid Caliph Abu Ja'far al-Mansur, who agreed to his request. After the liberation of these cities from the rebels, at the Tang court's request, the soldiers of the caliphate remained in China [Yan Beizhong 1992: 61], and their descendants later became part of the local Muslim population.

Given the political and economic situation in the country, the Tang Empire made changes to its tax policy. Until 834, the Tang dynasty imposed duties on Muslim traders arriving by sea, not only for entry into the country but also for departure. Starting from that year, taxes on Muslim traders were only collected for the ir arrival in the state. This was enough to stimulate the rapid development of free trade in China.

Changes in the Tang Empire's Internal Situation and the Rise of the Yuan Dynasty:

In 847, local Muslims were allowed to serve in government institutions and participate in exams for filling administrative positions within the state structures. One of the first participants in such exams to receive positive evaluations from the commission was Li Yangsheng (the Muslim name is unknown), who was of Arab origin [Zhongguo 1997: 5–10]. The worsening internal situation in the early 10th century and the intensification of civil wars led to the destruction of the Tang Empire and its fragmentation into 15 smaller territories. This period in China is referred to as the period of the "Five Dynasties and Ten Kingdoms" ("Wudai Shigu") [Shang Yue 1954: 179]. The two kingdoms that emerged afterward – the Northern and Southern Song (960–1279) – were unable to become as powerful as the Tang Empire. These circumstances significantly weakened the economic position of Xi'an and its international trade.

Conclusion. A state of equal power to the Tang Empire was established in China only at the end of the 13th century. This was the Yuan Empire (1279–1368), founded by the Mongols. The capital of the new empire was chosen to be Beijing, which led to the reduction of Chang'an's (Xi'an's) status as the capital of the empire. However, its role in international trade remained very important.

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